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THE CONCEPT OF ARTISTIC IDEAL IN CREATING A FEMALE IMAGE

Shahnoza Choriyeva,

An English Teacher at Uzbekistan State World Languages University,

Doctor of Philosophy in Philological Sciences (PhD)

sh.choriyeva@uzswlu.uz

Abstract: The article analyzes the unique artistic portrayal of the image of women in the English “Lost Generation” literature using the examples of the works of Richard Aldington and Vera Britten. The article conducted on the writing style and artistic skills in the works of R.Aldington and V.Brittain and the characteristics of “Lost Generation” literature in both creators' poetic and prose works are original for their time.

Keywords: “Lost Generation”, interpretation, artistic image, aesthetic ideal, main character, realistic portrait, triangle, female characters, pre-war period, autobiographical novel.

Introduction

In artistic literary work the concept of “image” appears as a multifaceted general moral category that is “fixed” in the human mind. In modern studies, “artistic image” can be interpreted differently. That is why scientists widely use various field methods to study these concepts. In literature, the worldview of the writer, which cannot be considered outside of the composition of the work, is interpreted through his artistic concepts. Literary critic Kazoqboy Yoldosh emphasizes that the author’s ideal plays an important role in the interpretation of the content of an artistic work: *“Artistic works often express the views of the characters that belong only to themselves and are completely unrelated to the author. However, in the science of literary recognition and the practice of teaching literature, it is often the case that one or another character’s word or thought is accepted as the idea of the whole work. It should be borne in mind that in very few cases the author trusts the hero to express the idea of the work or a part of this idea, for this the author needs to be strongly united with his hero in the work, a kind of autobiographicalism”* [4, 69]. It is worth noting that the artistic ideal of Richard Aldington and Vera Britten is the image of the main character, which vividly expresses the aesthetic views of the authors. The beginning that encouraged artists to pick up a pen is an aesthetic ideal, and the artistic symbols created by them are a means of realizing the aesthetic ideal.

Researcher A. Akhmedova defines the ideal hero as follows: “The ideal hero is not the image of a person completely free of flaws and defects, but the image of the main character who vividly expresses the aesthetic views of the author. The ideal hero reflects the author’s dreams of truth, beauty and goodness. The image of an ideal hero represents an ideal, in particular, the ideal of the author. As artistic creation

arises from the need to express an aesthetic ideal, it is naturally observed that it is reflected more or more brightly in some images” [1, 29].

Materials and methods

V. Britten begins the novel “Testament of Youth” with a legendary story about a girl named Katerina meeting a magical woman. She asked: “*Which would you rather have – a happy youth or a happy old age?*”. Katerina answered: “*If I say a happy youth, then I shall have to suffer all the rest of my life. No I will bear trouble now, and have something better to look forward to*”. So, she looked up and said: “Give me a happy old age” [3, 27]. The author skillfully emphasizes that this legend is about the young girl Vera herself and that she and her peers were deprived of a happy youth because of the war.

In her work, V. Britten remembers that she studied at a special school for girls, describes the school uniform from the language of the author-narrator even before the war, and notes that such a uniform did not like her and made her angry. The rules of the past were alien to her, forcing her to wear woolen underwear, black cashmere socks, woolen clothes. In particular, she reflects on dark cloth trousers, flannel skirts and other things typical of that time. Through this, she tried to reveal the inner taste and spirit of girls and women of that time. V. Britten effectively uses the speech of the author-narrator to describe the reality of her time. Through the metaphor of “local and family attention” in the work, she was able to show all the hopes, aspirations and personal relationships of women.

V. Britten suffers from the fact that the woman and her realistic portrait during the war and after the war are not fully disclosed through her works, and she reacts to this situation as follows: “*The war was a stage of life in which the experience of women was radically different from that of men, and I mainly focus on women. I am not claiming equality of suffering and service when I point out that depictions of the war years are incomplete because they ignore relevant aspects. The woman who shows the war in its true form in her life and illuminates its importance for her generation once again is silent and she is still silent*” [3, 132].

When she wrote these thoughts in 1931, she started her book and intended that her artistic ideal would be a woman, as she describes it. Of course, “Testament of Youth” was far from the only type of story of a woman’s military experience created up to that time, although it was the most famous. It should be noted that in V. Britten’s “The Testament of Youth” men occupy a central place in the system of images. Although she started writing the book with a female theme, she later connected the relationship of both genders to the era and the war in a coherent plot line. Certainly, nothing in the literature of the First World War can so vividly describe the path from the destruction of the illusions of heroism, from self-inflicted guilt, to the despair and depression of the survivors, and the futile sacrifice of the dead.

In general, V. Britten, who left a deep mark on English literature, is literally different from other writers because she was able to create the image of a woman with an inner conflict in her psyche through her work “Testament of Youth”. Writers who lived before or after V. Britten also created the image of a woman in their works, but this writer, unlike them, was able to clearly and clearly show the specific features of the spirit of the time in the image of a woman. In the image of the main character, two different character traits are summarized, that is, the dynamics of Vera’s money described at the beginning of the work develops vertically during the course of events. Stubborn, did not want to get married at all, could not bear to stifle her freedom, relentlessly strives for her goal, because of the suffering of war, Vera is deep-thinking, calm, restrained, and a friend becomes a noble Vera who can lend a helping hand to the enemy as well. The fact that the female characters are enriched with realism and psychologism in V. Britten’s work “Testament of Youth” can, on the one hand, be considered the high skill of the writer, and on the other hand, it can show the artistic uniqueness of these characters. Therefore, the image of women occupies the main place in V. Britten’s works.

Unlike V. Britten's novel "Testament of Youth", R. Aldington's "Death of a Hero" has three main female characters, who are embodied as characters who play an important role in discovering and shaping the character of George Winterbourne. They are George's mother Isabelle, his wife Elizabeth and his lover Fanny, and this "triad of women" has a strong place in the life of George Winterbourne, that is, George Winterbourne is at the center of the triangle of female characters, and each of them is a person of the main character of the work in a certain place and time. plays an important role in its formation.

Main part

Isabel Hartley Winterbourne is the mother of George Winterbourne, the main character of the play, and the wife of George Augustus Winterbourne. The first chapter of the novel describes George's family. Although his father is a representative of the middle class, his mother Isabel thinks that she is marrying the son of a rich family. *"Isabel Hartly was one – don't ask which in numerical order, or by which wife – of Captain Hartly's daughters. She was very pretty, in a florid, vulgarish way, with her artful-innocent dark eyes, and flashing smiles, and pretty little bustle and frills, and 'fresh complexion' and 'abounding health. She was fascinatingly ignorant, even to the none too sophisticated George Augustus"* [2, 68].

George Augustos falls madly in love with her. Believing in his wealth, Isabel agrees to marry him. After George is born, she meets several men in her life and betrays her husband. When the son learns this truth, he hates his mother. That is why he left his home and came to live in London. R. Aldington's parents were considered the prototypes of George Winterborn's parents, and the author hated his parents as well as the hero of the work.

The dynamics that give rise to George's actions are played out through the women's relationship to him and to other members of society. Taking this into account, we can come to the conclusion that the "triad of women" are characters who create actions, and George himself is a character who moves under the influence. R. Aldington writes his book to tell the truth about the past war and to prevent a new war. R. Aldington, addressing the people who survived the war, forces them to think about the causes of the war and its culprits. *"Why did the war start? Who was responsible?"* such questions repeatedly appear in front of the reader on the pages of the work. *"The whole world is guilty of bloodshed,"* concluded R. Aldington, without excluding any of his contemporaries from such guilt. The writer does not know the ways to prevent the military threat, but he is persistently looking for them. Through his work, he makes a meaningful contribution to the solution of the most important task of the time. He describes this situation in this way: *"That is why I am writing the life of George Winterbourne, a unit? One human body murdered, but to me a symbol. It is an atonement, a desperate effort to wipe off the blood-guiltiness. Perhaps it is the wrong way. Perhaps the poison will still be in me. If so, I shall search for some other way. But I shall search"* [2, 24].

The news of George's death is also analyzed through the reaction of those three women in the prologue of the play. George wanted to punish everyone with his own death. He was dissatisfied with his family, friends, and society. For him, the war is a place where he can escape from all his problems, an opportunity to rediscover his identity, and gives him the impression that they help him like friends. It wasn't just George's death, it was the untimely sunset of all the memories associated with him, the hopes for tomorrow, and the dawns that have not yet dawned.

The conclusion that all those who died in the war are heroes and those who returned are the living dead rises to the level of the leitmotif of the work. When the issue of war and female characters in the works of R. Aldington and V. Britten is cross-referenced, while R. Aldington emphasized the image of female characters mainly in the events of the pre-war period, V. Britten herself is the central character. as an autobiographical novel looks at the events and problems of the time from a woman's point of view and analyzes them based on their minds and emotions. The sad fate of the hero of R. Aldington is not only the war, but also the women in his life. As for V. Britten, she suffers greatly from the death of four

important people in her life - four men, although the war is over and victory is celebrated, and he cannot forget the disasters caused by the war.

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